

Preprint of: Kazem, Hussein A., Jabar Yousif, Miqdam T. Chaichan, and Ali HA Al-Waeli. "Experimental and deep learning artificial neural network approach for evaluating grid-connected photovoltaic systems." *International Journal of Energy Research* 43, no. 14 (2019): 8572-8591.

Link: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/er.4855>

Experimental and Deep Learning Artificial Neural Network Approach for evaluating grid-connected photovoltaic systems

Hussein A. Kazem^{1,2*}, Jabar Yousif¹, Miqdam T Chaichan³, Ali H A Al-Waeli²

¹Sohar University, PO Box 44, Sohar, PCI 311, Oman

²Solar Energy Research Institute, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia, 43600, Bangi, Selangor, Malaysia

³Energy and Renewable Energies Technology Research Center, University of Technology, Iraq

Abstract

This article evaluates a 1.4 kW building integrated grid-connected photovoltaic plant. The PV plant installed in Faculty of Engineering solar energy lab, Sohar University, Oman and the system data has collected for a year from July 2017 to June 2018. The grid-connected system was evaluated in term of power, energy, specific yield, capacity factor, and cost of energy, and payback period. The measured diffuse and global solar irradiations are 3289 Wh/m² and 6182 Wh/m², respectively. Four predictive models (TLRN, FRNN-1, FRNN-2 and FRNN-3) using deep learning approach based on RNN and TLRN were proposed to predict the PV current performance through data input of temperature (T) and solar irradiance (G). The experiment results found that the highest energy production, array, reference, and final yields are 245.8 kWh, 3.43-5.65 kWh/kWp-day, 4.61-7.33 kWh/kWp-day, and 3.24-4.82 kWh/kWp-day, respectively. Meanwhile *CF*, *CoE* and *PBP* found to be 21.7%, 0.045 USD/kWh and 11.17 years, respectively. The highest performance for prediction models were found for FRNN-2 and FRNN-3 due to exhibits lower MSE which means being tightly fitted to experiments.

Keywords: Desert type PV; Grid connected PV; PV performance; deep learning

Source: Kazem, Hussein A., Jabar Yousif, Miqdam T. Chaichan, and Ali HA Al-Waeli. "Experimental and deep learning artificial neural network approach for evaluating grid-connected photovoltaic systems." *International Journal of Energy Research* 43, no. 14 (2019): 8572-8591.

Link: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/er.4855>

1. Introduction

One of the most attractive applications of PV systems is building integrated photovoltaic (BIPV), which has undergone rapid developments in recent years. However, BIPV has experienced quick advancements as of late; regardless, BIPV systems have been progressively created [1]. The performance of the PV unit is considered the primary and vital issue as the performance of these units deteriorates over time as they are affected by weather conditions (temperature, relative humidity, dust, etc.) [2]. The high temperature of the photovoltaic unit by 10°C results in a 5% decrease in electrical efficiency [3]. Also, dust accumulation is strongly depending on the location of the installed PV system, wind speed, etc. [4]. High temperature and dust accumulation cause losses in module performance and attributed to external conditions. Many researchers conducted massive research works to assess the performance of GCPV systems and determine the impact of variable factors such as general efficiency, life cycle costs, energy cost, energy recovery period. Ref. [5] conducted a critical review study to demonstrate the importance of grid-related PV systems and potential problems at high load levels and ways to prevent the disruption of these photovoltaic systems. The study focused on ways to improve conversion efficiency and overall harmonic tension.

Several research groups from variable countries (Turkey [6], Spain [7], United Arab Emirates (UAE) [8], Oman[9], and Kuwait [10, 11] conducted an economic, technical evaluation of a photovoltaic system connected to the network. The researchers presented an analytical presentation of weather data for the area where the system has constructed. In their studies, they found that their systems can achieve between 4 % to 8% of the average monthly value of electricity demand. References [12 & 13] were interested in many air parameters effects such as solar radiation intensity, ambient temperature, and tilt angle of the photovoltaic cells. Both studies proved that the efficiency of electricity generation depends mainly on the solar radiation intensity and in a lower extent on the ambient temperature.

References [14-17] evaluated the performance of many photovoltaic modules attached to the grid. Ref. [14] concluded that the use of monocrystalline/noncrystallized silicon technology is the best technique that can be linked to a grid. Ref. [15] concluded that the photovoltaic system that uses crystalline cells generates more energy than a system that uses monochromatic cells. However, Ref. [16] after conducting practical experiments, concluded that the photovoltaic system made of multi-crystalline cells was found to produce higher yields than the non-crystalline silicon cell system.

Ref. [17] found that the copper-indium-delineated (CIS) cells system generated more energy with a higher efficiency ratio than a monocrystalline cell system. Ref. [18] demonstrated that the photovoltaic system with 1006.74 kW of crystalline silicon (c-Si) photovoltaic cells (installed in semi-arid climates in India) has deteriorated based on observation data. The minimum PV degradation has ranged from -0.30% to -0.17% starting from the third year of operation, which is an acceptable limit according to previous studies [19, 20].

Artificial neural networks (ANN) are essential mathematical models for simulating the human brain. Artificial neural networks have been widely used in applications such as data classification, pattern recognition, predicting future values, control, operation, etc. The neural network learned by processing a set of inputs with the ability to handle these inputs according to the model and structure of the neural network and then generate the output. Furthermore, the existence of intermediate hidden neurons is useful to reduce errors and accelerate learning by adjusting the weights of each neuron and rebuild the new weight values. However, there are two main types of ANN architecture, feed-forward, and feed-backward (Recurrent) [21]. Ref. [22] conducted a deep review of the ANN applications used in literature to predict the performance of solar collectors and to use this technique to know the depth of distance between the capabilities of this technique and the practical results. The study concluded that the articles reviewed in the study confirmed that ANN technique could be considered a very appropriate method to predict the output of solar collectors. In this framework, References [23 & 24] used the artificial neural network (ANN) based Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) method to predict the output of several photovoltaic systems (traditional PV, water-cooled PVT, nanofluid cooled PVT, and nanofluid + nano-PCM cooled PVT) at the same environmental conditions. The researchers used several verification methods to ascertain the results of the proposed model. The results of the proposed model are entirely consistent with the experimental results of the study. Also, their proximity to the results of published works in literature, as the authors have claimed. The results of the analysis showed that the sensitivity of the primary system is to the intensity of solar radiation followed by the ambient temperature. Ref. [25] developed an artificial neural network (ANN) model consisting of three layers to estimate the products of the glass-based PVT-TEC. The researchers studied the thermal energy, electric and outgoing exergy gain of the system. The researchers rely on changing weather conditions (ambient temperature, diffuse solar radiation, and global solar radiation) for New Delhi-India in their study. They analyzed the complex relationships of the effect of these conditions on PVT collector components. The ANN model used resulted in a consistent accuracy prediction result, with a high correlation of ($R = 0.9997$) and mean square error of ($MSE = 0.86 \times 10^{-1}$).

Deep learning is part of machine learning methods that automatically learn data representations based on learning data by deploying a multi-layered neural network. It is classified into supervised, semi-supervised, or unsupervised [26]. Ref. [27] has introduced the concept of deep learning to detect network disruption, a combination of wavelet conversion, multi-resolution single-universe, and deep-learning geometry. The simulation results in this study proved that the use of this concept can achieve the desired goal and is very accurate. Ref. [28] was concerned with building a model that predicts the output of a photovoltaic system and adopted in building this model on the extreme learning machine (ELM). The results of the proposed model were compared with the results of other studies that adopted different models, such as the support vector regression (SVR), and artificial neural network (ANN). The study found that the proposed ELM model has higher predictive accuracy and a lower arithmetic time than the output power generated by the photoelectric system.

Ref. [29] used a group consisted of deep learning algorithms such as MLP, Deep Belief Networks, AutoEncoder, and LSTM to predict and use them in the renewable energy field. The study aimed to show the strength of these approaches compared to the physical prediction model. The comparison was made by forecasting the power output of 21 photovoltaic power plants. The results of the study showed that the use of Deep Learning algorithms gives superior prediction compared to physical models and ANN.

It is essential to study and predict power generated from GCPV systems to serve to establish large scale PV plants [30]. Modeling, optimization, technical, and economic investigations are highly needed to evaluate the operation and performance of these systems [31, 32]. These studies will help to adjust large scale PV systems and future projects [33, 34].

This paper aims to evaluate GCPV systems' potential in Oman depending on practical measures, which will be used in Deep learning program. A 1.4 kW GCPV will be evaluated in Sohar in the north part of Oman. The data collected for one year from July 2017 to June 2018 will be used to evaluate the performance of the system. The prediction of the outputs of power plants using renewable energies has become a very active research field, as it gives reliable data on the energy generated from these stations with safely operating of the energy network. This approach helps to reduce the operational costs of these power plants. Many vital studies [35-39] have confirmed that deep learning algorithms are excellent in predicting such topics. Unfortunately, to date, the application of a deep learning approach to predicting the outcomes of photovoltaic stations connected to the grid has only been narrowly applied. Deep learning technique is used in this article to evaluate and predict the system output.

2. Experimental Setup

2.1 The used PV system

The consumption of crude oil and natural gas dominated Oman's energy production mainly by 65% for oil and 35% for gas in 2011 [40]. Efforts to eliminate carbon and integrate renewable energy are on-going but on a small scale. Oman Electricity Regulatory Authority (ORA) said in its annual report for 2012 that the country is seeking to diversify electricity generation and reduce dependence on gas and oil. Renewable energy sources can serve a lot in achieving these goals [41]. Thus, the use of different types of renewable energy technologies is essential. Solar energy can be a viable energy alternative for countries like Oman, which have high solar radiation. Photovoltaic (PVGC) systems are starting to spread in the GCC region. Specifically, in Oman, in line with the Sultanate's vision for the year 2030, Oman plans to produce electricity using photovoltaic (PV) modules up to a few gigawatts [41].

One of these projects is the grid-connected PV system installed in Sohar University to the north of Oman at the latitude of 24.3461° N, and longitude of 56.7075° E. KD 140GH-2PU solar modules were installed to supply peak power of 140 W and 12 V DC at standard test conditions, as Figure 1 reveals. To maximize the average annual power output of photovoltaic units, they were installed at a fixed tilt angle equal to the latitude of + 3° and facing the real south, as recommended by Ref. [42]. The PV modules are connected in series to provide enough input voltage to the grid-connected inverter. A 10 PV modules are connected in series to provide 177 V DC (17.7 Vmp×10) the input voltage to the Sunny Boy 1700 inverter. Table 1 illustrates the PV and inverter specifications.

Table 1 Specifications of the proposed system

PV array (Kyocera KD140GH-2PU)	
PV.module.rated.power (10 modules)	140 Wp (1.4 kWp)
Maximum.voltage	17.7
Maximum.current	7.91
Open.circuit.voltage	22.1
Short.circuit.current	8.68
PV module.efficiency	13.9%
Temperature.coefficient of Vo.c	-0.36 %/k
Temperature.coefficient of Is.c	0.06 %/k
Inverter	1.7 kW
AC.voltage	220-260
Inverter.efficiency	94.1%

Figure 1. Grid-connected PV system.

2.2 Sohar metrological data

Oman is in the south-eastern part of the Arabian Peninsula, between latitudes 21.4735° N north and longitudes 55.9754° E east, covering an area of 309,500 km², 82% of which is covered in desert. Solar irradiance data is usually found as daily average values for all months during the year. Thus, the specific hours where the radiation is at its maximum, which is usually at noon, must be taken into account. A readiness assessment report from the IRENA regarding Oman [43] has

shown that solar irradiance in Oman changes during the year from as low as 2.37 kWh/m²/day to as high as 7.34 kWh/m²/day, with Sohar being the 3rd highest city in terms of solar irradiance. Figure 2 illustrates the average daily ambient temperature, diffuse, and global solar irradiances on 23rd April 2018. It has found that diffuse and global solar irradiances are 3289 Wh/m² and 6182 Wh/m², respectively. Furthermore, Sohar average daily wind speed, humidity, pressure, and dew found to be 14 km/h SE, 40%, 1016 mb, and 57%, respectively.

Figure 2. Sohar profiles for solar radiation and ambient temperature.

2.3. Performance evaluation criteria

The IEC 61724 “International Electrotechnical Commission” 1998 defined the evaluation criteria for the grid-connected PV systems, which contains energy production (E) and yields (SY), performance ratio (R), cost of energy (CoE), life cycle costs (LCC) and recovery period (PBP), present worth (MC), percentage value of the replacement cost (RC), efficiencies (η), losses (P_{loss}) and capacity factor (CF) [37, 38]. These criteria defined in equations (1) to (12), respectively.

$$YF_d = \frac{E_{PV}(\text{kWh/year})}{PV_{WP}(\text{kWp})} \quad (1a)$$

$$YF_F = \frac{E_{AC}(\text{kWh/year})}{PV_{WP}(\text{kWp})} \quad (1b)$$

$$YR = \frac{G_T}{G_{STC}} \quad (1c)$$

The specific factor (*SY* or *YF*) definition is “the annual, monthly or daily net AC energy output of the system divided by the peak power of the installed PV array at standard test conditions (STC)”. Where: YF_d , YF_F and Y_R are array, final and references yields, respectively. Also, the capacity factor (*CF*) estimates benefits obtained from the system and is known as: “the ratio of the actual annual energy output to the amount of energy the PV array would generate if it operated at full rated power (P_R) for 24 h per day for a year”. The performance ratio (P_R) defined as “the standard employed to evaluate the used PV system quality”.

$$CF = \frac{SY}{8760} = \frac{EPV_{annual}}{(P_R \times 8760)} \quad (2)$$

$$PR = \frac{SY}{Y_R} \quad (3)$$

The *LCC* is calculated by equation (4):

$$LCC = C_{capital} + \sum_1^n C_{O\&M} \cdot R_{PW} + \sum_1^n C_{replacement} \cdot R_{PW} - C_{salvage} \cdot R_{PW} \quad (4)$$

$$R_{PW} = F / (1+i)^N \quad (5)$$

$$C_{capital} = CA_i \times UC_i + ICI \quad (6)$$

$$MC_r = MC_{0r} \times \left(\frac{1+f}{i-f} \right) \times \left[1 - \left(\frac{1+f}{1+i} \right)^N \right] \quad (7)$$

$$MC_{0r} = k_r \times IC_r \quad (8)$$

$$MC = \sum_1^r MC_r \quad (9)$$

$$RC_k = IC_k \times \sum_{j=1}^{N_r} \left(\frac{1+FR}{1+IR} \right)^{\left(\frac{LP \times j}{N_r + 1} \right)} \quad (10)$$

$$RC = \sum_{k=1}^2 RC_k \quad (11)$$

The cost of energy calculates as follows:

$$CoE = \frac{LCC}{\sum_1^n E_{PV}} \quad (12)$$

The PV generated power calculated by:

$$P_{PV}(t) = P_{peak} \left(\frac{G(t)}{G_{stc}} \right) - \alpha_T [T_c(t) - T_{stc}] \quad (13)$$

The T_c is calculated by:

$$T_c(t) - T_{amb} = \left(\frac{NOCT-20}{800} \right) G(t) \quad (14)$$

Also, the PV electrical power generated is calculated in equation (15) in the form of set of time periods (hour, day or month):

$$E_{AC,t1} = \sum_{t=1}^N E_{AC,t2} \quad (15)$$

Where, $N= 60, 24$ and 30 for hour, day and month, respectively. Finally, PV array and system efficiencies calculated in equations (16) and (17).

$$\eta_{PV} = \frac{E_{DC}}{G(t) \times A_c} \times 100\% \quad (16)$$

$$\eta_{sys} = \frac{E_{AC}}{G(t) \times A_c} \times 100\% \quad (17)$$

2.4. Deep Learning method

In some cases, the model used should have some internal memory to store and update context information, which is achieved by feeding the network with a delayed vector (tapped) of the past observations. The feedforward is central to the feedback mechanism of the neural system that makes it heterogeneous to a deeply recurrent biological neural network. Thus, both the feedforward and feedback path can be employed in the recurrent neural network. The feedback path can be initiated at any layer as a feed to a previous layer, as shown in Figure 3. [44]. The Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) is biologically more realistic and computationally more effective since it is created on neurons with feedback connections. Investigation on RNN has proven that the network can undertake application that is highly dependent on sequence information and memory. Since RNN can unfold in time and accept a sequence of input patterns, therefore, it is the most preferred method to predict the next step using the simple recurrent neural network (SRNN). The SRNN is made-up of an input layer, a fully connected hidden layer, and an output layer. It merely uses the weight, which is attached to the gradient of the error to determine and reduce further errors using the Backpropagation through time (BPTT). Another type of recurrent neural networks is called fully recurrent neural networks (FRNN), which provide two-way connections between the layers in the neural network. Similarly, the partial recurrent neural networks (PRNNs) have attracted a great deal of attention. The PRNNs have the benefit of more organized recurrent links, through accelerating learning and causing fewer stability problems. A subset of the units is assigned as the input layer, and they are committed to the specified input values. The data passes to all adjacent connected layers and flows back and forth until the layers stabilize.

For the sake of network stabling, the activations of the hidden and output layers are recomputed until the network stabled [45]. LSTM shows a reliable and adaptive facilities to learn and remember information over the time using BPTT. The LSTM uses a memory cell, which is made up of a complicated form of the node model. The current neuron of the neural network will be substituted by these “memory cell”. Each memory cell contains self-recurrent connection at a fixed weight, which allows the memory cell to maintain its value regularly. The recurrent neural networks with long short-term memory (LSTM) have recently expanded as a robust and scalable model for diverse learning problems related to sequential data. LSTM is effective at learning temporal dependencies with the advantage that they do not experience the optimization Barriers of the simple recurrent networks and have been employed to solve countless problems. Time lagged recurrent networks (TLRNs) are MLPs extended with short term memory structures and local recurrent connections. The input layer used the inputs delayed by multiple time points before presented to the network. Most real-world data contains information in its time structure; that is how the data changes with time [46].

TLRNs are state of the art in nonlinear time series prediction. It is a gradient descent technique to minimize some error criteria. The general network architecture has three layers, and the feedback connection from the hidden layer back to the input layer. Training of the TLRN was done with Backpropagation through time with trajectory learning parameters. Backpropagation training involves information processing in two directions, the feedforward of the input information and the Backpropagation of the error. The input information is processed in the input neurons o and is passed down to the next layer through the links.

Figure 3. Re-current neural network architecture

RNN learn from sequences of experimental data, which represents as a set of (X_i, O_i) pairs, where X_i is the input data at the time (i) , and O_i is the desired output. The output of RNN is defined as in equation (18)

$$O^t = f(h^t; \theta) \dots \tag{18}$$

h^t is the value of the hidden layer(s) at time t , which is computed as in equation (19).

$$h^t = g(h^{t-1}, X^t; \theta) \dots \quad (19)$$

is the implemented transfer function.

Back-propagation through time (BPTT) based the gradient for each weight is summed over the back-step copies between the successive layers and the weights are adapted using the formula for the back-propagation with a momentum term after each pattern. Therefore, the output at the time $(t + 1)$ based on the current input and previous output defined in equation (20).

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial w_{ij}} = \sum_{k=1}^T \delta_i(k) * f'(net_i(k)) * x_j(k-1) \dots \quad (20)$$

The $\delta_i(k)$ is the error propagated by the transpose network across the network and through time. Since the activations $x(k)$ in the forward pass have been stored, the gradient across time can be reconstructed by simple addition.

The error correction learning work $y_i(n)$ is the response at PE_i at iteration n and the desired response $d_i(n)$ for a given input pattern, and an instantaneous error is defined as in equation (21):

$$e_i(n) = d_i(n) - y_i(n) \quad (21)$$

The updating of the weights values using momentum learning method is defined in equation (22).

$$w_{ij}(n+1) = w_{ij}(n) + \eta \delta_i(n) + x_j(n) + \alpha(w_{ij}(n) - w_{ij}(n-1)) \quad (22)$$

Where the local error $\delta_i(n)$ is computed from $e_i(n)$ at the output PE as in equation (21). The α is the momentum learning rate, which is to be set between 0.1 and 0.9. The step size η is a constant value which is usually set to 1.

Different methods have been implemented and designed for computing the performance of ANN, which mainly includes MSE, NMSE, MAPE, R, R^2 , MAPE, and RMSE. The mean square error (MSE) estimate the moment of the error measured, which is determined in equation (23).

$$MSE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - x_i)^2 \quad (23)$$

Where n is the number of datasets, y_i is the predictions value, and x_i is the desired value.

The root means absolute error (RMSE) is used to determine the average value of the errors which is calculated by equation (24).

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (Y_i - X_i)^2} \quad (24)$$

The absolute mean percentage error (MAPE) is measured the degree of the forecasting precision, which is computed by the equation (25).

$$MAPE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^N \left| \frac{x_i - y_i}{x_i} \right| \quad (25)$$

Where x_i is the desired output and y_i is the forecast output.

The correlation coefficient (R) is in range [-1, 1], high value is preferred, which is defined as in equation (26).

$$r = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{(\sum_{j=1}^n (x_j - \bar{x})^2 \cdot \sum_{k=1}^n (y_k - \bar{y})^2)^{1/2}}, \{-1 \leq r \leq 1\} \quad (26)$$

The coefficient of determination (R^2) assesses the validity of the predictive results compared to the experimental (desired) output, which is defined by equation (27).

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_i^n (x_i - y_i)^2}{\sum_i^n (x_i - \bar{x}_i)^2} \quad (27)$$

where $\bar{x}_i$ is the mean of desired output.

The Normalized Mean Square Error (NMSE) is determined the overall differences between the predicted and desired values, which computed as in equation (28).

$$MSE(\hat{y}) = \frac{100}{N\sigma_y^2} \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 \quad (28)$$

Where σ is the Standard deviation, N the number of data, y_i is desired output, and $\hat{y}_i$ is the predicted output.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Experimental results

A system of sensors was connected to a different part of the GCPV to measure and downloaded the electrical parameters at 15 minutes intervals. Figure 4 shows the PV (DC) and inverter (AC) electrical powers measured for 30 days (January 2018). It is found that the DC and AC powers are close since the inverter efficiency is high, which mean lower losses. Besides, the power production is relatively high even though January is in the winter season where the weather is relatively cloudy and solar irradiation is lower comparing with summer. In entire year, the best period of power and energy production was summer (May to October) with 245.8 kWh in June, where the solar irradiation is relatively higher and reflected positively of the PV power production. Also, it was recorded that the lowest power and energy production recorded in winter (November to February) with 224.5 kWh in February.

Figure 4 One-month (April 2018) power productions for PV (DC) and inverter (AC).

The AC voltage and frequency of the system is depicted in Figure 5(a), which shows high consistency. According to the finding in Figure 4(a), the average daily AC voltage and frequency are 49.98 Hz ($\pm 0.02\%$) and 248.58 V ($\pm 0.21\%$), which comply with electricity regulation in Oman. Also, PV module current measured and recorded every second, as shown in Figure 5(b). It is seen that the current has the same pattern of solar irradiance, with peak current 7.70 A in the middle of the day.

(a)

(b)

Figure 5. PV System (a) AC voltage and frequency, (b) DC Current

Figure 6 shows the variation of the measured PV system power, energy, and solar irradiance for a particular day in June 2017. In June the solar irradiance peak in the middle of the day at 1158 W/m². However, the temperature is relatively high, which reduce power and efficiency. The power and energy curves rely upon solar irradiance, and they are in consistence with more flatten energy curve early morning and late afternoon. This situation is due to the variation in temperature and solar irradiance in these periods of times.

Figure 6. PV system power, energy and solar irradiance

A one whole year of PV system yield shown in Figure 7. The array, reference, and final yields varied between 3.43 to 5.65 kWh/kWp-day, 4.61 to 7.33 kWh/kWp-day, and 3.24 and 4.82 kWh/kWp-day, respectively. The yield is directly proportional to the solar irradiation, where it found that the system yield is relatively high compared with similar systems in literature [47, 48, and 49]. Meanwhile, *CF*, *CoE*, and *PBP* found to be 21.7%, 0.045 USD/kWh, and 11.17 years, respectively.

Figure 7. Grid-connected PV system and monthly performance

The annual average of the performance ratio found to be 0.67 varies between 0.53 in June and 0.71 in January. It is relative, low in summer and high in winter, which relies on the high temperature and system losses in summer compared with the situation in winter.

The average monthly efficiency of the GCPV system (PV and Inverter) for one full year shown in Fig. 8. The GCPV array efficiency varied from 9.1% to 10.8%. Also, the maximum and minimum efficiencies found in December and July, respectively. There is a dispute that solar radiation is higher in July than in December, but the weather is more dusty and warmer in July, which will negatively impact GCPV energy production and efficiency this month. Besides, the inverter efficiency varied from 91% to 94%.

Figure 8. PV and inverter average monthly efficiencies.

3.2. Deep learning design and results

This paper deployed Deep learning approach based on RNN and TLRN for predicting the behavior of current production in PV/T systems. For training and testing the neural models, 1000 of cleaned data sets is used, which classifies into three classes (60% for training, 30% for cross-validation, and 10% for testing). These data undertaken is collected every 15 minutes on the data set. The maximum value of epochs is set to be 1000 in these experiments. Also, the number of the hidden layer should be between the number of the input and the output variables — the architecture of the RNN neural network is depicted in Table 2. The inputs consist of two factors: solar radiation (G) and ambient temperature (T), and its output from one factor that is current (I). The momentum learning method in the hidden layer was applied at an educational rate of $\alpha = 0.7$ and step = 1, to update the weight values on the different layers. The transfer function used is TanhAxon as hidden layers and output. A momentum deployed as a learning function with the rate of $\alpha = 0.7$, and a step size of 1. All proposed neural models tested at the same condition's irradiance, ambient temperature for systematic analysis.

Table 2 Summary of ANN architecture of proposed predicting models.

	RNN	TLRN
Input variables	Solar irradiance (G), Temperature Ambient (T))	Solar irradiance (G), Temperature Ambient (T))
Output variable	Current (I)	Current (I)
Number hidden of Layers	1 and 2	1 and 2
Transfer Function	TanhAxon	TanhAxon

Number of epochs	1000,5000,10000	1000
Learning Algorithm	Momentum $\alpha = 0.7$, and a step size = 1	Momentum $\alpha = 0.7$, step size = 1
Number of data sets	1000 pair (600 for training, 300 for cross-validation, and 100 for testing)	1000 pair (600 for training, 300 for cross-validation, and 100 for testing)

Different experiments have carried for the sake of checking the consistency and repeatability of the predicted results. However, the architecture of the network utilizes based on the trial and error process to adjust the values of parameters. Therefore, many changes must arrange before the final network can be implemented. These changes could involve the number of input and output variables. Also, it can adjust the number of hidden neurons or the number of epochs. Besides, data cleaning is a necessary process to ensure that the data will reflect and deploy real experimental data [50]. The cleaning process includes standardized the format and the unit of data. Also, remove incomplete data sets or data with zero values or empty. The data undertaken is cleaned data of seven days. In most cases, the network initializes random values for weights, which will lead to some oscillation in network output at the beginning of the training step. After several of epochs, the weight values will be adjusted accordingly.

Figure 9. Desired Output and Actual TLRN Network Output (based on 15 minutes measurement).

Figure 9 illustrates the comparison results of the experimental results of the “current” variable and the output of the proposed TLRN neural model. It shows there is some oscillation in the production of first epoch and after that, the results were stabilized and fitted the experimental data tightly. The maximum output of current is about 8, and the minimum value is around 1. The time is recorded every 15 minutes.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 10. Comparison of the desired and actual output currents (a) FRNN-1, (b) FRNN-2, and (c) FRNN-3 (based on 15 minutes measurement).

Figures 10 (a, b, c) illustrate the comparison results of the desired results of the current and the output of the proposed neural models based RNN entirely. The three neural models were smoothly predicted the desired production of current to distinguish between the output of neural models. In order to obtain the smallest value of mean square error (MSE), then we should determine the optimum number of epochs. It will help to avoid the overtraining of the network. Therefore, different experiments presented with different epochs (1000, 5000, 10000). Figure 10.a shows the output of FRNN with 1000 epochs, and Figure 10.b shows the output of FRNN with 5000 epochs. Also, Figure 10.c shows the output of FRNN with 10000 epochs. As a result of deploying different numbers of epochs, the value of MSE has decreased accordingly. They obtained promising MSE of 0.0038, 0.0026, 0.0017, and 0.0017 accordingly. The MSE amount reduced from 0.0038 to 0.0017, which affects the performance of the neural network model. Also, The NMSE presents the most prominent variations among models. Therefore, a low value of NMSE is preferable and shows that the model is well-performing. Also, the proposed models achieved encouraging NMSE results of 0.0138, 0.0099, 0.0095, and 0.0084 consequently, which means that the proposed models performed very well in predicting the desired data. Figure 11 (a, b) summaries the comparison of the MSE and NMSE and the correlation rate (R) of the three proposed models.

MSE & NMSE of experimental and proposed models

(a)

(b)

Figure 11. Comparison of the (a) MSE and NMSE of proposed models; (b) correlation rate (R).

Table 3 the comparison statistics of proposed predicting models.

	No. epoch	Final MSE	R	NMSE
TLRN	1000	0.00383	0.9946	0.01387
FRNN-1	1000	0.00265	0.9955	0.00996
FRNN-2	5000	0.00170	0.9956	0.00952
FRNN-3	10000	0.00174	0.9961	0.00843

Table 3 presents the comparison results of proposed predicting models (TLRN, FRNN-1, FRNN-2, and FRNN-3), which indicates that the proposed models have high correlation rate (R) of 99% with the desired results. This situation means the proposed models have a strong relationship with the relative movements of the experimental variable (Current). However, a high number of epochs help to enhance the performance by decreasing the MSE of proposed models as shown in Figure 11.b. Besides, the proposed models obtained a low rate of mean square errors based on the maximum MSE of 0.0038 and a minimum of 0.0017 accordingly. The obtained results show that the FRNN-2 and FRNN-3 models were achieved the highest performances in comparison to LRTN and FRNN-1. The lowest value of MSE means the closer fit to the experimental data.

Table 4 the descriptive statistics of quantitative data.

Statistic	Exp curr.	TLRN	FRNN-1	FRNN-2	FRNN-3
No. of observations	100	100	100	100	100
Minimum	0.0512	0.2452	0.0720	0.0264	0
Maximum	7.7023	7.2505	7.4328	7.3901	7.3522
1st Quartile	0.0576	0.3520	0.2856	0.2586	0.2323
Median	1.0474	0.8510	0.8926	0.8497	0.9143
3rd Quartile	5.7563	5.8388	5.6541	5.7523	5.9149
Mean	2.6588	2.7166	2.6885	2.7067	2.6924
Variance (n-1)	8.6945	7.7224	8.0050	8.2412	8.1896
Standard deviation (n-1)	2.9486	2.7789	2.8293	2.8707	2.8617

The data analysis aims to utilize statistical, and logical methods that help to summarize, evaluate and validate the obtained output. Table 4 presents the Quantitative descriptive statistics of the results of the four proposed models with experimental results in terms of current production. In statistics, the term “Mean” is the average of data sets, which is computed by divide the total of values by the number of these values. Also, the term “Variance” is used to measure the distance of each value in data set from the mean. Likewise, the term “standard deviation (SD)” merely is computed the positive value of the square root of the variance. It is useful for comparing the spread of two data sets around the mean. A small amount of SD means the narrower spread of measurements around the mean. Figure 12 shows the comparison of the Mean, Variance, and SD values.

Figure 12. The comparison of the Mean, Variance and SD values

The number of observations is 100. The values of current in experimental and proposed models are in the range of 0 as minimum value, and 8.7 as the maximum value. The interquartile range (IQR) describes the spread of data in the middle (50%) of ascending ordered values, which is the difference between the 3rd Quartile and 1st Quartile. Therefore, IQR for experimental results is (0.0576 - 5.7563), which equal to 5.6987. Also, the proposed models (TLRN, FRNN-1, FRNN-2, FRNN-3) were achieved IQR of (5.4868, 5.3685, 5.4937, 5.6826) respectively. The IQR values of proposed models were tightly fit the IQR value of experimental current. So, middle (50%) of data were spread equally, which means the results of the proposed models were to train and simulate the experimental data very well.

Figure 12 illustrates that the output of the standard deviation of the four proposed models was closely spread on the mean of experimental data of (current). The output obtained by the proposed models has smaller differences between the values of mean and standard deviation values in comparison with the results of experimental data. Therefore, the SD value of the TLRN model (2.77) fitted with the mean value of experimental output (2.71). Also, the SD value of FRNN-2 model (2.8) is confirmed the mean results of experimental production (2.71)). Besides, the other two models have achieved minimal differences between the SD and mean values. Also, Figure 12 shows that the obtained values of variance were better spread out training sample related to the original full experimental data. It clearly shown that predicting four models were forecasting the experimental output of recurrent strictly and followed the standard deviation values of experimental data of (current) about 2.86.

Table 5 the goodness statistics of fit proposed models

	TLRN	FRNN-1	FRNN-2	FRNN-3
Observations	100.0000	100.0000	100.0000	100.0000
DF	97.0000	97.0000	97.0000	97.0000
R ²	0.9892	0.9931	0.9912	0.9927
SSE	8.2188	5.4675	7.1538	5.9529

One of the most critical procedures is measuring the rate of how good the simulation model fits the experimental results. Table 5 describes the effects of the goodness test parameters of the four predicting models to meet the experimental desired data of the "current" variable. The coefficient of determination (R^2) depicts that all the four predicting models were (99%) fits the data of experimental test of "current" variable smoothly, which means there is a strong positive relationship between them. The degree of free (DF) is 97 of 100 observations. Sum of Squares Error (SSE) measures the total difference between the response values and the fit values. The proposed models (TLRN, FRNN-1, FRNN-2, and FRNN-3) obtained 0.0821, 0.0546, 0.0715, and 0.0595 accordingly. A small SSE value close to 0, means that the predicted model is more useful for fitting the experimental data.

Also, in order to ensure that the four predicting models fit the desired experimental data, then non-linear regression mathematical models were developed and evaluated under the same environment as shown in Figure 13 (a, b, c and d). The proposed predicting mathematical models were fitted with the proposed neural models and obtained excellent results, as illustrates in Table 6. Figure 13.a shows the relation between the predicted non-linear model for the TLRN neural model and the experimental data. It closely follows the desired output, which means that the neural network models and its proposed mathematical model fitted with the experimental data. Figure 13.b shows a close relationship between the predicted non-linear model for the FRNN-1(using 1000 epochs) neural model and the experimental data, which describe a well-fitting of the neural network models and its proposed mathematical model to the experimental data. Also, Figure 13 (c, d) sections present a smooth prediction for the experimental data using both the neural network models and its proposed mathematical models of FRNN-2 (using 5000 epochs) and FRNN-3 (using 10000 epochs), respectively.

(b)

(c)

Figure 13. The P-P plot of (a) Pred(TLRN-1000) / TLRN-1000, (b) Pred(TLRN-1000) / TLRN-1000, (c) Pred(FRNN-5000) / FRNN-5000, (d) Pred(FRNN-10000) / FRNN-10000.

Table 6 Proposed mathematical models.

Model Name	Proposed mathematical models
TLRN-1000	$TLRN -1000 = 0.23076 + 0.92195 * Exp\ curr + 0.00221 * Exp\ curr^2$
FRNN-1000	$FRNN -1000 = 0.17326 + 0.89132 * Exp\ curr + 0.00928 * Exp\ curr^2$
FRNN-5000	$FRNN -5000 = 0.12595 + 0.97810 * Exp\ curr - 0.00126 * Exp\ curr^2$
FRNN-10000	$FRNN -10000 = 0.09300 + 1.03665 * Exp\ curr - 0.01000 * Exp\ curr^2$

(a)

(b)

Figures 14. The comparison results of proposed predicting models (based on 15 minutes measurement).; a:using 1000 epochs ;b: using different number of epochs

Figure 14.a illustrates the time-series graph of the proposed models (SLM-1000, PRNN-1000, and FRNN-1000) and the experimental desired output using 1000 epochs. It is implemented base on the same environmental conditions to examine the performance of the solar system under the same conditions, which shows an excellent fitting relationship of the predicting models to the experimental data of “current” variables. The experimental data was painted with black color and dashed line style, while the predicting models were painted using different marker symbols for more clarifications. The proposed models achieved significant MSE results (0.0847, 0.0652, 0.0564), respectively. Also, Figure 14.b shows the time-series graph of the four proposed models (TLRN, FRNN-1, FRNN-2, and FRNN-3) and the experimental output of “current” using variance number of epochs. The comparison was performed under different numbers of epochs to determine the effects of increasing the number of epochs on the performance of the solar system. There are some oscillations in the middle of Figure (time from 27 to 67). However, the oscillation occurred because of adjusting the weight of the hidden layers and the recurrent process. However, it was evident that the proposed models were fitted with the experimental data carefully. The obtained MSE results of the proposed neural models (TLRN, FRNN-1, FRNN-2, and FRNN-3) were 0.0038, 0.0026, 0.0017, and 0.0017 accordingly. Also, they achieved high positive correlation rate (R) of 0.9946, 0.9955, 0.9956, and 0.9961 with the desired results, respectively.

Finally, to examine the effectiveness of the proposed models in predicting the amount of solar cell production, a comparison was made with some models in different regions using the same method. Also, the results were compared with other some works using different neural network prediction methods to examine the effects at different conditions, which gives more confidence in the results derived from the proposed methods. Table 7 concludes the comparison study with some selected works. Figure 15 shows the results of comparison of current proposed work with some chosen profession, which proved that the present results were precise and close fit the results of other researches. However, the results not give a clear indicate because of the variation in environmental conditions.

Table 7 Comparison of the Proposed models with some researches.

Reference No	Location	ANN/Solar Method	Variables	Finding
Behrang [51]	Iran/Dezfull	MPL, RBF/GSR	T, RH, G, WS,	R ² : 0.9957 MSE: 0.00395
Rahimikhoob [52]	Spain/Almeria	RNN/GSR	T	R ² : 0.8890 MSE: 6.4009
Assi [53]	UAE /Al-Ain	MLP RBF/GSR	T, RH, WS	R ² : 0.9212 MSE: 0.0729

Saberian [54]	Malaysia	GRNN, FFBP/GSR	T, G	R ² : 0.9994 MSE:0.000141
Kazem [55]	Oman/Sohar	SVM/RBF	T, G	R ² : 0.9991 MSE: 0.0007
Current Proposed Models	Oman/Sohar	FRNN,	T,G	R ² : 0.993 MSE: 0.0563
		PRNN	T, G	R ² : 0.992 MSE: 0.0652

Figures 15. The comparison results of proposed predicting with some selected works.

4. Conclusion

This paper presents the evaluation of a 1.4 kW GCPV plant installed in Sohar, Oman for a period of 1 year from July 2017 to June 2018. The evaluation is carried out to determine the cost-effectiveness of GCPV systems in hot climate conditions through the facilitation of technical and economic parameters. A Deep learning approach used for predicting the performance of PV plant employing RNN and TLRN; creating four predictive models. The prediction made in terms of current behavior through the use of weather data, mainly temperature (T) and solar irradiance (G). Moreover, the work presents the developed non-linear regression mathematical models which were used to ensure that predictive models fit

the experimental data. The technical findings from the experiments and calculation show that highest final yield, reference yield, array yield, and energy production to be around 3.24-4.82 kWh/kWp-day, 4.61-7.33 kWh/kWp-day, 3.43-5.65 kWh/kWp-day and 245.8 kWh, respectively. The estimated costs of energy and payback period were found to be 0.045 USD/kWh and 11.17 years, respectively. The four predictive models (TLRN, FRNN-1, FRNN-2, and FRNN-3) achieved an MSE of 0.0038, 0.0026, 0.0017, and 0.0017, respectively. While, the correlation rate (R) for the models was found high achieving 0.9946, 0.9955, 0.9956, and 0.9961, respectively. FRNN-2, and FRNN-3 models exhibit higher performance in comparison to LRTN and FRNN-1 given they tightly fit the experiments.

This study provides a pathway for prediction of GCPV systems' performance using deep neural networks and investigating the current behavior as output concerning the variation of temperature and solar irradiance. The reliability of such PV systems is an essential topic for industrial, commercial and residential applications and research towards assessing the scope and size of affects environment pose on PV systems is critical for further development, specifically in the middle-east and typical regions of relatively high ambient temperatures and solar irradiance levels, or general rural and desert climates.

Declaration of interest statement

“We the authors declare no affiliations with or involvement in any organization or entity with any financial interest (such as honoraria; educational grants; participation in speakers' bureaus; membership, employment, consultancies, stock ownership, or other equity interest; and expert testimony or patent licensing arrangements), or non-financial interest (such as personal or professional relationships, affiliations, knowledge or beliefs) in the subject matter or materials discussed in this manuscript”.

Conflict of Interests

“The authors declare that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this paper”.

Acknowledgment

“The research leading to these results has received Research Project Grant Funding from Sohar University SUSF-2018-01 and the Research Council of the Sultanate of Oman, Research Grant Agreement No. ORG SU EI 11 010”.

References

- [1] Kumar, N. M., Gupta, R. P., Mathew, M., Jayakumar, A., Singh, N. K., 2019. Performance, energy loss, and degradation prediction of roof-integrated crystalline solar PV system installed in Northern India, Case Study in Thermal Engineering, 13, 100409.
- [2] Kumar, N. M., Prabakaran, N., Jerin, A. R. A., Jayakumar, A., Impact of Performance Degradation and Capital Subsidy on the Revenue of Rooftop PV System. International Journal of Renewable Energy Research, 9(1), pp. 128-136.

- [3] Al-Waeli, A. H. A., Chaichan, M. T., Sopian, K., Kazem, H. A., 2018. Comparison study of indoor/outdoor experiments of SiC nanofluid as a base-fluid for a photovoltaic thermal PV/T system enhancement, *Energy*, 151, 33-44. DOI:10.1016/j.energy.2018.03.040
- [4] Kazem, H. A., Chaichan, M. T., 2019. The effect of dust accumulation and cleaning methods on PV panels' outcomes based on an experimental study of six locations in Northern Oman. *Solar Energy*, 187, pp. 30–38.
- [5] Eltawil, M. A., Zhao, Z., 2010. Grid-connected photovoltaic power systems: Technical and potential problems—A review. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 14(1), 112-129.
- [6] Celik, A.N., 2006. Present status of photovoltaic energy in Turkey and life cycle techno-economic analysis of a grid-connected photovoltaic-house. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 10(4), 370-387.
- [7] Sidrach-de-C, M., López, L. M., 1998. Evaluation of a grid-connected photovoltaic system in southern Spain. *Renewable Energy*, 15(1-4), 527-530.
- [8] Al-Sabounchi, A. M., Yalyali, S. A., Al-Thani, H. A., 2013. Design and performance evaluation of a photovoltaic grid-connected system in hot weather conditions. *Renewable energy*, 53, 71-78.
- [9] Kazem, H. A., Albadi, M. H., Al-Waeli, A. H. A., Al-Busaidi, A. H., Chaichan, M. T., 2017. Techno-economic feasibility analysis of 1 MW photovoltaic grid connected system in Oman, *Case Study of Thermal Engineering*, 10, 131-141. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.csite.2017.05.008>
- [10] Al-Otaibi, A., Al-Qattan, A., Fairouz, F., Al-Mulla, A., 2015. Performance evaluation of photovoltaic systems on Kuwaiti schools' rooftop. *Energy Convers Manage*, 95, 110–119.
- [11] Al-Hasan A. Y., Ghoneim A. A., Abdullah, A. H., 2004. Optimizing electrical load pattern in Kuwait using grid connected photovoltaic systems. *Energy conversion and management*, 45(4), 483-494.
- [12] Sulaiman, S. I., Rahman, T. K. A., Musirin, I., Shaari, S., Sopian K., 2012. An intelligent method for sizing optimization in grid-connected photovoltaic system. *Solar energy*, 86(7), 2067-2082.
- [13] Chakkaravarthy, A. N., Subathra, M. S., Pradeep, P. J., Kumar, N. M., 2018. Solar irradiance forecasting and energy optimization for achieving nearly net zero energy building. *Journal of Renewable and Sustainable Energy*, 10(3), 035103.
- [14] Rotogeropoulos, C., Klonaris, I., Petrocheilos, C., Charitos, I., Martinac, I., 2010. Performance evaluation of different PV module technologies in a grid-connected pilot project in Greece. In: 25nd European photovoltaic solar energy conference. Valencia, Spain; p. 6–10.
- [15] Komoni, V., Krasniqi, I., Lekaj, A., Gashi, I., 2014. Performance analysis of 3.9 kW grid connected photovoltaic systems in Kosova. In: *Renewable energy congress (IREC), 2014 5th international*; p. 1–6.
- [16] Tripathi, B., Yadav, P., Rathod, S., Kumar, M., 2014. Performance analysis and comparison of two silicon material based photovoltaic technologies under actual climatic conditions in Western India. *Energy Convers Manage*, 80, 97–102.
- [17] Humada, A. M., Hojabri, M., Hamada, H. M., Samsuri, F. B., Ahmed, M. N., 2016. Performance evaluation of two PV technologies (c-Si and CIS) for building integrated photovoltaic based on tropical climate condition: a case study in Malaysia. *Energy Build.* 119, 233–241.
- [18] Kumar, N. M., Malvoni, M., 2019. A preliminary study of the degradation of large-scale c-Si photovoltaic system under four years of operation in semi-arid climates. *Results in Physics*, 12, 1395-7.
- [19] Kumar, N. M., Sudhakar, K., Samykano, M., 2019. Performance comparison of BAPV and BIPV systems with c-Si, CIS and CdTe photovoltaic technologies under tropical weather conditions. *Case Studies in Thermal Engineering*. 13, 100374.

- [20] Kumar, N. M., Subathra, M. S. 2019. Three years ahead solar irradiance forecasting to quantify degradation influenced energy potentials from thin film (a-Si) photovoltaic system. *Results in Physics*, 12, 701-3.
- [21] Wu, W., Liao, W., Miao, J. and Du, G., 2019. Using Gated Recurrent Unit Network to Forecast Short-Term Load Considering Impact of Electricity Price. *Energy Procedia*, 158, pp.3369-3374.
- [22] Ghritlahre, H. K., Prasad, R. K., 2018. Application of ANN technique to predict the performance of solar collector systems - A review. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 84, pp. 75–88.
- [23] Al-Waeli, A. H. A., Sopian, K., Yousif, J. H., Kazem, H. A., Boland, J., Chaichan, M. T., 2019. Artificial neural network modeling and analysis of photovoltaic/thermal system based on the experimental study. *Energy Conversion and Management*, 186, pp. 368–379.
- [24] Al-Waeli, A. H. A., Kazem, H. A., Yousif, J. H., Chaichan, M. T., Sopian, K., 2020. Mathematical and neural network modeling for predicting and analyzing of photovoltaic/thermal (PV/T) systems performance. *Renewable Energy*, 145, 963-980.
- [25] Dimri, N., Tiwari, A., Tiwari, G.N., 2019. An overall exergy analysis of glass-tedlar photovoltaic thermal air collector incorporating thermoelectric cooler: A comparative study using artificial neural networks. *Energy Conversion and Management*, 195, 1350–1358.
- [26] Đozić, D. J. and Urošević, B.D.G., 2019. Application of artificial neural networks for testing long-term energy policy targets. *Energy*, 174, 488-496.
- [27] Kong, X., Xu, X., Yan, Z., Chen, S., Yang, H., Han, D., 2018. Deep learning hybrid method for islanding detection in distributed generation. *Applied Energy*, 210, 776–785.
- [28] Hossain, M., Mekhilef, S., Danesh, M., Olatomiwa, L., Shamshirband, S., 2017. Application of extreme learning machine for short term output power forecasting of three grid-connected PV systems, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 167, 395-405.
- [29] Gensler, A., Henze, J., Sick, B., Raabe, N., 2016. Deep Learning for solar power forecasting—an approach using AutoEncoder and LSTM Neural Networks. In 2016 IEEE international conference on systems, man, and cybernetics (SMC) 2016 Oct 9 (pp. 002858-002865). IEEE.
- [30] Kazem, H. A., Yousif, J., 2017. Comparison of prediction methods of photovoltaic power system production using a measured dataset, *Energy Conversion and Management*, 148, 1070–1081.
- [31] Charalambous, P. G., Maidment, G. G., Kalogirou, S. A., Yiakoumetti, K., 2007. Photovoltaic thermal (PV/T) collectors: A review. *Applied Thermal Engineering*. 27(2-3), 275-286.
- [32] Kazem, H. A., Khatib, T., Sopian, K., 2013. Sizing of a standalone photovoltaic/ battery system at minimum cost for remote housing electrification in Sohar, Oman. *Energy and Building*, 6C, 108-115.
- [33] International Electrotechnical Commission 1998, IEC 61724, “IEC 61724, photovoltaic system performance monitoring guidelines for measurement, data exchange and analysis (1st ed.). Geneva: IEC: International Electrotechnical Commission.
- [34] Kazem, H. A., Khatib, T., Sopian, K., Elmenreich, W., 2014. Performance and feasibility assessment of a 1.4kW roof top grid-connected photovoltaic power system under desertec weather conditions. *Energy and Building*, 82, 123-129.
- [35] Qiu, X., Ren, Y., Suganthan, P. N., Amaratunga, G. A., 2017. Empirical mode decomposition based ensemble deep learning for load demand time series forecasting. *Applied Soft Computing*, 54, 246-255.
- [36] Yang, H. F., Chen, Y. P., 2019. Hybrid deep learning and empirical mode decomposition model for time series applications. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 120, 128-138.

- [37] Långkvist, M., Karlsson, L., Loutfi, A., 2014. A review of unsupervised feature learning and deep learning for time-series modeling. *Pattern Recognition Letters*, 42, 11-24.
- [38] He, Y., Mendis, G. J., Wei, J., 2017. Real-time detection of false data injection attacks in smart grid: A deep learning-based intelligent mechanism. *IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid*, 8(5), 2505-2516.
- [39] Wang, S., Fan, S., Chen, J., Liu, X., Hao, B., Yu, J., 2018. Deep-learning based fault diagnosis using computer-visualised power flow. *IET Generation, Transmission & Distribution*, 12(17), 3985-3992.
- [40] Authority for Electricity Generation, Annual Report 2012, <http://www.aer-oman.org>, retrieved on 22nd April 2018.
- [41] International Energy Agency (IEA), Oman: Balances for 2011, <http://www.iea.org>, retrieved on 22nd April 2018.
- [42] E. Kymakis, S. Kalykakis, T. Papazoglou, Performance analysis of a grid connected Photovoltaic Park on the island of Crete, *Energy Conversion and Management* 2009; **50**:433-438.
- [43] Ministry of National Economy. <http://www.moneoman.gov.om>. Accessed 26th February 2019.
- [44] Al-Waeli, A. H. A., Kazem, H. A., Chaichan, M. T., Sopian, K., 2020. *Photovoltaic/Thermal System: Principles, Design and Applications*, 1st Edition, Springer Nature, ISBN: 978-3-030-27824-3.
- [45] Ruíz, L.G.B., Capel, M.I. and Pegalajar, M.C., 2019. Parallel memetic algorithm for training recurrent neural networks for the energy efficiency problem. *Applied Soft Computing*, 76, pp.356-368.
- [46] Greff, K., Srivastava, R.K., Koutník, J., Steunebrink, B.R. and Schmidhuber, J., 2016. LSTM: A search space odyssey. *IEEE transactions on neural networks and learning systems*, 28(10), pp.2222-2232.
- [47] Al-Waeli, H. A., Kazem, H. A., Sopian, K., Chaichan, M. T., 2018. Techno-economical assessment of grid connected PV/T using nanoparticles and water as base-fluid systems in Malaysia. *International Journal of Sustainable Energy*, 37(6), 558-578.
- [48] Tavanaei, A., Ghodrati, M., Kheradpisheh, S. R., Masquelier, T., Maida, A., 2019. Deep learning in spiking neural networks. *Neural Networks*, 111, 47-63.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neunet.2018.12.002>.
- [49] Al-Badi, A. H., 2018. Measured performance evaluation of a 1.4 kW grid connected desert type PV in Oman, *Energy for Sustainable Development*, 47, 107–113.
- [50] Sheela, K.G. and Deepa, S.N., 2013. Review on methods to fix number of hidden neurons in neural networks. *Mathematical Problems in Engineering*, Article ID 425740, 11 pages.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1155/2013/425740>.
- [51] M.A. Behrang, E. Assareh, A. Ghanbarzadeh, A.R. Noghrehabadi, The potential of different artificial neural network (ANN) techniques in daily global solar radiation modeling based on meteorological data , *Sol. Energy*, 84 (8) (2010), pp. 1468-1480.
- [52] A. Rahimikhoob, Estimating global solar radiation using artificial neural network and air temperature data in a semi-arid environment, *Renew. Energy*, 35 (9) (2010), pp. 2131-2135.
- [53] Assi, A.H., Al-Shamisi, M.H., Hejase, H.A. and Haddad, A., 2013, October. Prediction of global solar radiation in UAE using artificial neural networks. In *2013 International Conference on Renewable Energy Research and Applications (ICRERA)* (pp. 196-200). IEEE.
- [54] Saberian, A., Hizam, H., Radzi, M.A.M., Ab Kadir, M.Z.A. and Mirzaei, M., 2014. Modelling and prediction of photovoltaic power output using artificial neural networks. *International journal of Photoenergy*, 2014.
- [55] Kazem, H.A., Yousif, J.H. and Chaichan, M.T., 2016. Modeling of daily solar energy system prediction using support vector machine for Oman. *International Journal of Applied Engineering Research*, 11(20), pp.10166-10172.

Nomenclature

PV	Photovoltaic	N	Number of years
GCPV	Grid-Connected Photovoltaic	N_r	The number of components replaced over the lifetime of the system
ANN	Artificial Neural Networks	$P_{in}(t)$	The instantaneous input power
V_{OC}	Open Circuit Voltage	P_{Inv}	The inverter power
I_{SC}	Short Circuit Current	$P_{loss}(t)$	The instantaneous power losses
MLP	Multilayer Perceptron	P_{PV}	The PV module power
SRNN	Simple Recurrent Neural Network	P_{peak}	The PV peak power
RNN	Recurrent Neural Network	$C_{salvage}$	The net worth of the system at the final year of project lifetime
FRNN	Fully Recurrent Neural Network	P_R	Rated power
PRNN	Partial Recurrent Neural Network	RC_k	The replacement cost of the k^{th} component (USD)
COE	Cost of Energy	R_{PV}	Performance factor
LCCA	Life Cycle Cost Analysis	t_1	The hour, day, month
SY	Specific Yield	$-t_2$	The minute, hour, day
CF	Capacity Factor	T	Temperature
MAPE	Mean Absolute Percentage Error	T_c	The cell temperature
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error	$T_{standard}$	The temperature of (25°C) at standard test conditions (STC)
MAE	Mean Absolute Error	G	The incident solar irradiance (W/m^2)
MSE	Mean Square Error	WS	Wind Speed
STC	Standard test conditions	RH	Relative Humidity
YF_d	The daily/monthly yield	E_{AC}	Alternating current energy
YF	The yield factor	E_{DC}	Direct current energy
YF_F	Final yield	$G_{standard}$	solar radiation ($1000 W/m^2$) at standard test conditions
YR	Reference yield	ICI	Total constant cost, including the cost of installation and civil works (USD)
MC	The system total maintenance cost	IC_k	The initial cost of the k^{th} component (USD)
MC_{or}	The maintenance cost of the r^{th} component in the first year (USD)	IC_r	The initial cost of the r^{th} component (USD)
MC_r	The maintenance cost (USD)	K	Value of 1 and 2, which are equivalent to the inverter and pump, respectively.
PBP	Payback period	CA_i	The capacity of the i^{th} component of SAPV, SAPVT nanofluid and nano-PCM
A_c	The collector area (m^2)	$C_{capital}$	The capital cost of a project
c_1, c_2 and c_3	The PV module coefficients	$C_{O\&M}$	The yearly operation and maintenance costs
k_r	A constant refers to the maintenance cost as a percentage of the initial cost of the r^{th} component	$C_{replacement}$	The cost of all equipment replacement and repair